

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SOME PECULIARITIES OF METAPHOR AND METAPHORICAL HYPERBOLE IN THE NOVEL “THE GREAT GATSBY” BY FRANCIS SCOTT FITZGERALD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878428>

Abstract

Figurative and expressive means of language are techniques that make it intuitive, imaginative and decorate evaluation and perception in a special way, attracting attention. Stylistic technique is an important tool in the process of creating a visual image of the character of the work. With the help of stylistic devices, the characters are characterized by recreating a living image.

Keywords: metaphor, hyperbole, metaphorical personification, irony, metaphorical simile

Nowadays the requirements of knowing language are growing and the necessity of reading literature is becoming natural for these learners who really want to know English well for communication with the native speakers. The authors made up their minds to consider the use of some lexical stylistic devices such as metaphors and metaphorical hyperbole in the novel “The Great Gatsby” by Francis Scott Fitzgerald.

The Great Gatsby is a novel by American writer Francis Scott Fitzgerald, which was published in 1925, and this novel is a classic representative of the so-called “Jazz Age” in American literature. The matter is that this novel is saturated with a great number of variety ways of descriptions. Let’s consider the following sentence!

My own house was an eye-sore, but it was a small eye-sore.

There is a metaphor “*My own house was an eye-sore*” in this abstract.

The character Nick Carraway in his speech compares the size of his house and the Gatsby Palace. Thus, one house is presented as a huge and magnificent mansion, and the other as a tiny inconspicuous house.

I enjoyed the counter-raid so thoroughly that I came back restless. [3, c. 10]

These words demonstrate a certain irritation, a sarcastic tone.

The lawn started at the beach and ran toward the front door for a quarter of a mile, jumping over sundials and brick walks and burning gardens—finally when it reached the house drifting up the side in bright vines as though from the momentum of its run.

“*Burning gardens*” means a lot of colors, bright attention-grabbing gardens.

I’ve been lying on that sofa for as long as I can remember.

Overstatement hyperbole highlights Daisy’s despondency, a prolonged pause in her life.

Tom’s getting very profound. He reads deep books with long words in them. We’ve got to beat them down.

A perfect example of verbal irony is shown. Daisy makes fun of Tom in a caustic manner. It is clear that

she does not support his judgments, however, judging by Tom’s irritation, she expresses it in a slightly venomously, sarcastic form.

That’s why I came over tonight. [3, c. 38]

Nick Carraway jokes while answering Daisy, who asked if he wanted to know the truth about the butler’s nose. That is, he says what he doesn’t really mean, therefore it is verbal irony.

Her family is one aunt about a thousand years old. [3, p. 52]

Trite hyperbole shows overstatement implying that the aunt is very old.

On Sunday morning while church bells rang in the villages along shore the world and its mistress returned to Gatsby’s house and twinkled hilariously on his lawn. [3, c. 148]

On such a morning there were so many people that it is compared to the whole world, they “*twinkled hilariously*”, which means that they brought gloss, fun and chic to the Gatsby house.

It was a rich cream color, bright with nickel, swollen here and there in its monstrous length with triumphant hatboxes and supper-boxes and tool-boxes, and terraced with a labyrinth of windshields that mirrored a dozen suns.

In the description of Gatsby’s car, the hyperbole “*monstrous length*” is used, which means an incredible capable of striking the imagination length, and “*dozen suns*” expression probably resulted from a multitude of reflections formed by “*labyrinth of windshields*”.

With fenders spread like wings we scattered light through half Astoria. [3, c. 168]

When it comes to driving speed, the inversion consisting of hyperbole gives the reader to understand how Nick imagined what they looked like from the observer angle. The car seemed to have wings, it seemed to fly, and obviously it was clean, well-groomed, shiny, therefore the text says “we scattered light”.

She dressed in white, and had a little white roadster and all day long the telephone rang in her house. [3, c. 184]

Of course, the phone cannot ring every second all day, it is implied that Daisy was popular and charming, enjoyed success in society.

He had become simply the proprietor of an elaborate roadhouse next door. [3, c. 158]

Such a seemingly ordinary comparison shows how much Nick got used to Gatsby, that neither his charm nor charisma overshadowed his personality anymore, he became a simple person for Nick, with whom there was nothing to talk about.

In the first half of the novel, a lot of space is devoted to the description of parties at Gatsby's house:

At high tide in the afternoon I watched his guests diving from the tower of his raft, or taking the sun on the hot sand of his beach while his two motorboats slit the waters of the Sound, drawing aquaplanes over cataracts of foam.

This description includes a metaphor expressed in the predicate "*split the waters*", and there is an almost complete identification of the concepts: cutting and rapid movement.

It is in the light of irony that the whole external aspect of Gatsby's life at the villa in West Egg is described. Among his numerous, smartly dressed guests, there is not a single memorable face. Their faces are like comic masks, merge and repeat, which exist insofar as the "Great" Gatsby exists, and after his death at the end of the novel disappear without a trace.

At intervals she appeared suddenly at his side like an angry diamond, and hissed: "You promised!" into his ear [3, c. 130]

Describing the voice of an angry wife with whistling-hissing sounds, that is, an implied metaphor, the author enhances the image by comparing it with a diamond cutting glass.

On buffet tables, garnished with glistening hors d'oeuvre, spiced baked hams crowded against salads of harlequin designs and pastry pigs and turkeys bewitched to a dark gold.

The famous celebrations at Gatsby's house stand out here, and the metaphors that occur, help to represent the author's attitude to the hero, and it still remains disapproving. Not only the festivities themselves are disapproved of, but also their host; irony can be traced.

The lights grow brighter as the earth lurches away from the sun and now the orchestra is playing yellow cocktail music and the opera of voices pitches a key higher. Laughter is easier minute by minute, spilled with prodigality, tipped out at a cheerful world.

The metaphorical personification "*the earth lurches away*" gives an idea of the duration of what is happening, introduces the reader to the atmosphere of the party. That is, the party continues even when it's dark.

In the second sentence, the metaphor "*spilled with prodigality, tipped out at a cheerful world*" emphasizes the lightness, carefree atmosphere of the evening, as well as the author's ironic, half-contemptuous attitude towards people spending time here, including the host of this evening.

He came alive to me, delivered suddenly from the womb of his purposeless splendor.

These are Nick's thoughts about Gatsby when he found out about his feelings for Daisy, his sadness and his dream. That is, Gatsby acquired some kind of integrity for Nick and a reason to be called a living person.

In the following example, there is already a slight shift in the application and formation of the metaphor:

The groups change more swiftly, swell with new arrivals, dissolve and form in the same breath: already there are wanderers, confident girls who weave here and there among the stouter and more stable, become for a sharp joyous moment the centre of a group, and then, excited with triumph, glide on through the sea-change of faces and voices and colour under the constantly changing light.

Now the metaphor reflects the still cautious, ironic and slightly contemptuous attitude of the author. The first metaphor "swell" is developed and concretized by the subsequent verb "dissolve", "*excited with triumph, glide on through the sea-change*".

In the metaphor "*the sea-change of faces and voices and colour*" the sea does not mean a body of water. Such a structure identifies the multitude, this is an ironic assessment by the author of the society gathered at Gatsby's house.

I went over to his lawn a little after seven and wandered around rather ill-at-ease among swirls and eddies of people I didn't know... [3, c. 102]

It is also used the identification of the set, which is expressed by nouns denoting a complex, intricate connection, the interweaving of an indeterminately large number of subjects.

In the second half of the novel, when the secret of Gatsby is partially revealed – his love for Daisy, the mood of the novel as a whole change, a change in the author's attitude towards his hero is felt, sympathy appears.

...decking it (his dream) out with every bright feather that drifted his way [3, c. 234]

Using the stylistic device of the metaphor "*decking out*", it is emphasized that Gatsby's dream was becoming more and more attractive.

He literally glowed; without a word or a gesture of exultation a new well-being radiated from him and filled the little room. [3, c. 218]

The metaphor "glowed" reveals its full meaning with the help of the subsequent metaphor "*a new well-being radiated, filled*", which indicates that he is glad to meet Daisy.

When he realized what I was talking about, that there were twinkle-bells of sunshine in the room, he smiled like a weather man, like an ecstatic patron of recurrent light. [3, c. 218]

Metaphorical simile, expressed by the saying "*weather man*", conveys the joy of the hero, his elated state.

It was strange to reach the marble steps and find no stir of bright dresses in and out of the door, and hear no sound but bird voices in the trees. [3, c. 222]

Another description of the set shows the author's previous attitude to the guests, the noisy crowd, for him they are only "*bright dresses in and out of the door*".

The sparkling odor of jonquils and the frothy odor of hawthorn and plum blossoms and the pale gold odor of kiss-me-at-the-gate. [3, c. 222]

With the help of participles, the aroma, condition, color and shape of the flowers themselves (narcissus, hawthorn, plum and honeysuckle) are transmitted.

In the last chapters, a tension is added to the approving-sympathetic attitude in anticipation of a tragic denouement.

But with every word she was drawing further and further into herself, so he gave that up, and only the dead dream fought on as the afternoon slipped away, trying to touch what was no longer tangible, struggling unhappily, undesperingly, towards that lost voice across the room [3, c. 330]

The expression "the dead dream fought on" is an ordinary transfer of meaning from one phenomenon to another. The verbs "drawing further, fought on, slipped away, trying to touch what was no longer tangible, struggling" give the whole sentence not only an evaluative coloring of sympathy and sympathy, but also hopelessness, gloomy foreboding. The same can be observed in the following metaphors:

He was clutching at some last hope and I couldn't bear to shake him free 'Jay Gatsby' had broken up like glass against Tom's hard malice. [3, c. 360]

Gatsby broke like glass, so he is depressed and in some kind of despair.

The ending of the novel is replete with metaphors expressing the collapse of hopes and dreams, all the drama and a sense of empathy for the hero is conveyed, and his isolation from the circle of famous and rich is felt more than in other chapters of the novel:

The track curved and now it was going away from the sun, which, as it sank lower, seemed to spread itself in benediction over the vanishing city where she had drown her breath. He stretched out his hand desperately as if to snatch only a wisp of air, to save a fragment of the spot. [3, c. 374]

In the first sentence, the part "sank lower, to spread itself in benediction" reflects the state of the environment, nature, the reader's introduction to the mood of the hero, his despair and the loss of the meaning of life.

Want to go with me, old sport? [3, c. 118]

Here it is possible to note a little joking, even ironic attitude of the speaker to his interlocutor.

The grass looks fine, if that's you mean. [3, c. 204]

The speaker wants to please his interlocutor, to inform him that the lawn around the mansion looks decent or even beautiful, or he likes the freshness and greenery of the grass, which the gardener so carefully monitors.

I hate careless people. That's why I like you. [3, c. 148]

The use of this verb "like" serves to describe the scene of the woman's confession that she really likes this young man, that maybe she is even in love with him.

Figurative and expressive means of language are techniques that make it intuitive, imaginative and decorate evaluation and perception in a special way, attracting attention. Stylistic technique is an important tool in the process of creating a visual image of the character of the work. With the help of stylistic devices, the characters are characterized by recreating a living image.

The frequently encountered contrasts reveal the inner inconsistency of Gatsby, the discrepancy between his thoughts about succeeding to win an imposed dream and his true motives, eternal moral values are clearly visible.

Most stylistic devices affect the emotional and expressive coloring of the word. Different meanings of the same words can differ markedly in stylistic coloring, in one sense the word appears as majestic, high, and in another - as ironic, mocking. Metaphorization also contributes to the development of expressive nuances in the semantics of words. Thus, stylistically neutral words with the help of metaphorization and hyperbolization acquire a vivid expression. A word exposed to a stylistic device can convey positive and negative emotions, contain an assessment, can be used to convey the author's attitude, irony, etc. The metaphor in the novel focuses on the absurdity of what is happening, the actions of the guests, how everything looks caricatured from the outside: these iridescent bright dresses, people intoxicated with glamour and brilliance, lights burning even brighter at sundown. Metaphors in the novel help to create vivid, memorable images. A metaphor serves to emphasize a feature, create an individual image, create an emotional effect, create a special sentiment.

The accentuation in the text is due to hyperbole. How majestic is Jay Gatsby's palace, how fast is his shining car that seems to fly on wings, or how long has Daisy been in sadness.

It is also obvious that the novel is saturated with irony. Remarkable descriptions convey this gloss and all the external beauty of the surroundings, of the jazz era itself. The behavior and reactions of the characters, especially the guests, how much they are mired in this race for imaginary greatness and prosperity, are ironic. Irony is identified with contempt for such a way of life. Irony, as a means of comic presentation of material, is a powerful tool for the formation of a literary style built on the opposition of the literal meaning of words and utterances to their true meaning.

Thus, based on the analysis carried out, it can be concluded that a distinctive feature of a work of art is a figurative and emotional impact on the reader, expressiveness, achieved by using a huge number of different stylistic techniques. An artistic text, being a fiction (although reflecting reality), provides particularly ample opportunities for freely depicting the passage of time and thus creating various stylistic effects. It is stylistic devices that are carriers of an expressive, bright valuable component of any work. Stylistic devices are an integral part of works of fiction.

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SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DEPENDENT PREPOSITIONS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878431>

Abstract

This article touches upon the relevant issue in the learning process. The aspect of dependent prepositions in the English language requires special attention in terms of their meaning in the context. The attempt is made to define the major characteristics of dependent prepositions taking into consideration figurative meaning and its classification.

Keywords: metaphor; metonymy; subjectification; derived; compound; composite

To use English effectively, it is important to master four language skills, namely listening, speaking, reading and writing. Of all the four language skills, writing is considered the most difficult process. The majority of students encounter difficulties in using prepositions in terms of semantic aspects. As for the dependent prepositions, they affect the meaning of the words with which they are associated, often changing their meaning beyond recognition. Dependent prepositions have a function in the construction of a sentence. The origin of this type of speech comes from the roots of words of ancient origin.

All English prepositions can be divided into simple, compound, derived and composite. The *simple* type has an overwhelming number of prepositions. These include, for example, *against* (*with, on, to, under*), the prepositions *in* (*for, on, at*), *about*. *Compound* consists of several components. These include *where upon* (*after which, as a result of which*), *within* (*in, inside*). *Derived* ones come from words of other parts of speech. These include, for example, *concerning* (*about, by*).

Composite type uses phrases when forming. They consist of a word from another part of speech and one or two prepositions. These include, for example, *because of* (*due to, because of*), *with regard to* (*in relation to*). Any element from a compound preposition cannot

be shortened or expanded – it is a single whole unit. The meaning of *composite* is directly dependent on the significant word that is part of it. Mainly the composite prepositions can be referred to dependent ones as they acquire the specific characteristics in the context. Some linguists call them prepositions with the metaphorical meaning [1]. The only way to distinguish between the primary and abstract meaning is to memorise prepositions, which is a challenge for students to rise to. A pedagogical strategy is essential for students to pay attention to the cooccurrence, collocation, and discourse behaviour of prepositions.

The group of researchers classifies dependent prepositions according to their structural characteristics. By prepositional use, they mean collocations, patterns and idioms containing prepositions: a) preposition + noun: *at risk, on time, out of tune* b) noun + preposition: *overview of, absorption of, an increase in, lack of* c) adjective + preposition: *associated with, responsible for, interested in* d) verb + preposition: *worry about, suffer from, get rid of, die out* e) chunk containing preposition: *on my own, in the long run, in contact with, on the verge of, to the point of* f) idiom containing phrasal verb: *clear up your act, hang out, turn down* [2].

To demonstrate the semantic shift in meaning, the following examples are given: